

Western Governors University Teachers College

Master of Science, Curriculum and Instruction

WGU Capstone Research

The Effects of Using Manipulatives in Classroom Instruction

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Abstract

This study showed the effects of using manipulatives in classroom instruction in teaching deoxyribonucleic acid or DNA structures and its function. Many students in high school are at risk of having a learning deficiency in the lesson as this lesson is normally being taught in the classroom using just concepts and sometimes pictures, physical and digital. This impacts the students' ability to be prepared for much more advanced science lessons such as genetics or mutation. In this research, I was able to focus on the effects of using manipulatives in teaching the topic DNA structure and its function. The method that was used in this research is quantitative design wherein 10 males and 10 females from the population of the 10th grade students in high school, whose ages are ranging from 14 -16 years old, taking Biology was given the intervention to address the students' learning deficiency in the lesson the structure of the Deoxyribonucleic Acid and its function. The data collected from the results of the pretest and posttest that was given to the learners before and after the intervention was implemented, as the baseline of the scores of the participants for their curve of learning. The research showed that using manipulatives improved the learning of the students as evident in the 7 points increase in the average scores of the participants.

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Chapter 1: Topic and Problem

Research Type

In this capstone research, I will be using action research with instructional intervention in addressing the problem stated below.

Research Topic

The topic structures of the deoxyribonucleic acid and its function is aligned with my subject Biology for high school as it is embedded in both the state standard and the Next Generation Science Standard that we are using in teaching the Science subject. Our DNA can unlock mysteries on how a person look different from his family or why a person has some rare disease. According to the Genes in Life (2022), it is important that we learn our family history as this data can provide us vital information for a better health related concerns or decisions that we will make (Genes in Life, 2022).

The Center for Disease Control (2021) stated that understanding factors affecting the genes and genetic disorders will have a positive impact in promoting health awareness and preventing diseases from occurring as some genetic changes are linked to some illness upon childbirth (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2021). This topic is important to the field of curriculum as it addresses the needs of the students in learning concepts on parts and structures of the DNA. This concept will enable the students to understand the core discipline of Genetics.

Problem Statement

There is a significant problem in my high school Biology students understanding the concepts of parts and structure of the deoxyribonucleic acid or DNA. This impact the students that need to learn the concepts of DNA to learn other concepts that has a

prerequisite of understanding the inheritance of traits. This may be happening because the teaching strategies used in the lesson is not sufficient to meet the needs of the standards.

Problem Impact and Root Cause(s)

The learning deficiency in the specific area, understanding the concepts and parts of the deoxyribonucleic acid, will impact the student's capability to understand the bigger concepts in science particularly Genetics as they are lacking the content knowledge on the prerequisite topic. Many topics in science are expressed in molecular level and that includes DNA. One of the root causes of this problem, is the way the topic is being presented in the classroom. The lack of manipulatives and or model that the teacher can use in teaching the concept itself. While other students may be able to grasp the concepts, some students are struggling in associating the concepts to the actual image of DNA.

Yero (2019) stated that the use of manipulatives is becoming more popular because students are actively involved in the learning process. The author also mentioned that by touching and exploring hands-on materials, children use their senses, which allows more cognitive connections to be made with a concept (Yero, 2019). Campbell University (2022) stated that the use of manipulatives in classroom instruction can be helpful in motivating the students to learn.

Research Question(s)

How does using models of the DNA impact the high school students taking Biology in understanding the concept of structures of the deoxyribonucleic acid or DNA and its function as measured by a pre/post assessment?

Justification

Many high school 10th grade students taking Biology are struggling in the topics in Genetics. As I narrow down my analysis on the problem, I have found out that the reason behind this is the learning deficiency in the prerequisite topic which is the structures of the DNA and its function. To address this concern, intervention has to be given to the learners. This can help the students have a better understanding of the lesson.

Chapter 2: Review of the Literature

Introduction to the Literature Review

Nourishing the students knowledge of understanding biological processes in a molecular level is greatly enhanced when they are given materialize that they can use for visualization. Ensuring that this learning experience will happen, is not easy. One of the major biological concept with which many students are struggling is the study of the relationship of DNA structure to it's function.

In a world that is constantly evolving with numerous scientific advancement and new studies in Genetics, I recognize that understanding the DNA structure and its function is important. This topic will prepare the students for a more challenging learning acquisition in Science in the future. Therefore, the students has to learn this molecular structure thoroughly as it plays a vital role in studying Genetics which is a prerequisite of other topics in Science like Evolution and Taxonomy.

Many research has shown that studying science without any intervention in teaching the concepts has resulted to a less desirable outcome. Many teachers and people that are in the field of education have used many strategies to address the fact that students cannot observe molecules and DNA with their naked eye. Educators have used strategies using simple manipulatives, computer simulations, 2D and 3D image or illustration and symbols for parts representation where studies shows that the growth in students understanding the science concepts has increased a lot.

In this proposed capstone, I describe an exercise that will help enhance my 10th grade high school students in Biology's understandanding the DNA structure and it's function using simple manipulatives in the classroom.

Thematic Subheading

As to teach DNA, their molecular structures and their functions, teachers have come up with different strategies including but are not limited to using cooperative learning, jigsaw puzzle, paper model, simple representations and even with the aide of computer through animation either 2D or 3D. This helped the students a lot in viewing DNA closer as they have something to manipulate. “A complete understanding of difficult topics in genetics can be achieved through using hands-on methods, problem solving, and inquiry based methods” (Hoppe, 2013, p.3).

Domenico (2003) mentioned that the traditional pencil and paper assessment alone do not give us an accurate data about the students' knowledge of science. Some researchers also used cut and paste paper model in teaching DNA. While this activity is very brief and simple, its value of clearly visualizing and illustrating the basic techniques of genetics concepts and biotechnology can not be disputed (Altiparmak & Nakiboglu Tezer, 2009). There were other studies that showed evidence of growth on the students' academic achievement including but are not limited to the availability of the resources, the physical manipulatives that is being used in the instruction and some are teacher factor. However, the success or failure of the use of the physical manipulatives in the teaching and learning process would also depends on the teachers' perception on their use (Tan, 2015).

It is well known that students often struggle with studying biological science concepts as a whole not just the topic on DNA. In one study, the students are having difficulties in distinguishing taxa of a tree. McLaurin (2015) mentioned on his research

Using Manipulative Models to Develop Tree-Thinking, that the use of multiple colors helped the students to easily track the lineages of the tree. (McLaurin, 2015).

In other topics of Biology, many have come up with different ways on using models as manipulatives as an add on for classroom instruction. In one research, they use toothpick chromosomes as a model to learn this biomolecular structure for students in middle school. “They help students avoid confusing the terms by providing a concrete representation of how the terms are related to each other” (Bryant, 2003, p.15).

Guzman & Bartlett (2012) stated that although simple manipulatives are often used in pre-college teaching, it is a different situation in college level. The authors also mentioned that many research found out that the use of multiple representations in teaching biological processes has impacted the students learning positively (Guzman & Bartlett, 2012).

“As students construct physical representations of concepts during manipulative activities, they resolve misconceptions associated with the language of the concept. Manipulative activities can also serve as effective vehicles for engaging students who come to the classroom with minimal understanding of the topic. A well-designed manipulative activity will build on a concept, taking it from the simplistic to the complex, thus incorporating all topic knowledge” (Krontiris-Litowitz, 2003).

Having been said that the use of this physical models can help the students understand DNA structure and function, a concept foundational to the field, a lot of educators have come up with different strategies in using structural representations.

“Such lessons include cardboard cut outs or computer based software to distinguish DNA and RNA bases and components of the sugar-phosphate backbone, tubing or string to represent supercoiled DNA or laboratory investigations of topoisomerase effects on DNA structure” (Howell et al., 2019, p.3). Modelling does not end after developing the first model; constructed model should be tested, evaluated and revised (Park et al., 2019). According from Scholastic Parent (2012), helping the learners develop their ability to connect and know what to do in case they forget the fact or procedure is necessary for the student growth and thus why it is important that they associate concepts to objects that can promote retention.

“Manipulatives are considered models used to teach an abstract topic or difficult content, which can be beneficial to students because the hands-on materials are an active way to learn the subject matter and to increase student engagement for science-related topics” (Kirk, 2015, p.5). Berk (1999) stated that the use of manipulatives made it possible to teach broad concepts in science instruction. “One of the arguments for the use of manipulatives in the classroom is that manipulatives provide an additional channel for conveying information” (Berkseth, 2013, p.3).

“Manipulatives are usually physical objects that students can investigate with their hands. They provide opportunities for students to grasp abstract ideas and translate them into concrete knowledge. For example, manipulatives can be as simple as marshmallows and toothpicks representing how atoms are bonded to one another, or they can be as elaborate as computer simulations that not only show how atoms are bonded, but describe their bond angles and geometries.” (Banks, 2014).

Conclusion

Learners, especially those that are in a very young age, learn most when they are given tangible materials or models to manipulate. The use of manipulatives help the learners have a deeper understanding by associating and representing molecular concepts into an object and afterwards transform it into a concrete knowledge. Manipulatives supports the students to see molecular parts and processes that cannot be seen by the naked eye. The students will show more academic progress when they have been exposed to physical materials or models, or a digital model may it be 2D or 3D that they can play around with in a computer, notebook or a tablet. This model will help the students gain knowledge academically as they tend to remember by associating their learning experience in the materials or manipulatives present at hand may it be simple or a complex one. This leaves a positive impact on the students' understanding of the DNA structures and its functions.

Chapter 3: Research Methodology

Research Question(s)

How does using models of the DNA impact the high school students taking Biology in understanding the concept of structures of the deoxyribonucleic acid or DNA and its function as measured by a pre/post assessment?

Participants or Stakeholders

There will be two stakeholders in my proposed capstone research. These are my 10th grade students taking Biology. This will consist of 10 males and 10 females which range from 13 to 16 years old. Their ethnicity is Native American. I have chosen them to be the participants in my capstone research because first, all of them are the ones that are required to get the credit from the subject and learn from the unit itself and secondly all of them can participate in the project as they are all in my class.

Data Collection Instrument(s) and Alignment to Research Question(s)

The questions on the assessments both pretest and posttest will be based on the concepts of the structure of the DNA and its function anchored by the discussion during classroom instruction using the manipulative models that was given to the students. The questions in the assessments will gauge the students progress before and after the intervention was given to the class. The questions will be aligned to the standard to address the learning deficiency as stated in the problem statement.

Method

The assessment that will be used for pretest and posttest will be used to collect data that I can use as a baseline of the scores of the participants and the curve of learning after the intervention. The pretest and posttest assessment will be a total of thirty items,

and this will be in the form of multiple-choice questions. The students will be given 60 minutes to take the test.

As a result of the aligned questions, the students progress based on the data collected should show the growth of the learner's knowledge acquisition and therefore ensuring that the students are ready for the more complex topic in science.

Data Analysis Technique(s)

I will be using descriptive statistics that will involves describing, organizing, and summarizing the data so it can be easily understood. I will be getting the mean of both pre and post assessment that will be given to the participants. If the mean obtained from the posttest is higher than the mean obtained in the pretest, therefore I can say that the intervention is effective and has a positive impact on the academic growth of the participants.

The descriptive statistics will help facilitate data visualization based on the results obtained from the pretest and posttest. It will provide a summary of the samples and the measures that was implemented on the study.

Timeline of Data Collection Activities

The data collection will be done the day before and the day after the actual day of the classroom instruction with intervention.

...Resources

The resources that I will need will include materials that I will be using digitally to represent the image of the DNA. The digital image should show the parts and function

of the parts of DNA. A powerpoint presentation that will anchor the lesson discussion will be prepared too. The assessment that will be used in the pretest and posttest must also be ready. The assessment will be the indicator of the baseline of the students knowledge and the curve of learning after the intervention. Last but the least, the materials that will be needed to create a model of the DNA which include but are not limited to strings, sponges, beads, buttons, glue, paper, scissors, strings and a plyboard for the stand. All of these materials are necessary for the successful implementation of the research.

Data Security and Confidentiality

The security and confidentiality of data for this action research will be stored properly in the isolation room before and after each use. The only time that it will be taken out from the storage area is when it is time to use it for referencing. The information that will be gathered during the execution of this action research will be confidential. The data gathered will solely be used by me, as the researcher. It'll not be shared to anyone. Any information that may lead to the identification of the subjects will be changed to codes to guarantee the privacy of the subjects as well.

Conclusion

This research will involve twenty students from high school taking Biology class. Each students will be given pretest wherein the scores from it will be use as the basis for learning growth once the intervention whis is the use of manipulatives in teaching structures of DNA and its function has been given. The learning growth will show how the use of manipulatives in classroom instruction particularly on the lesson should be able

to promote retention of knowledge to the students and that it should be able to address the learning deficiency of the students in the lesson.

Chapter 4: Results

Summary of Research

This research about the impact of using models of the DNA to the high school students taking Biology in understanding the concept of structures of the deoxyribonucleic acid or DNA and its function has seen to be effective based on the average scores I have gathered from the pre and post assessment administered before and after the intervention was given to the participants of this research. The average score of the pre-assessment showed that the participants were able to get 11 questions correctly. On the other hand, the post assessment showed that the participants were able to get 18 questions correctly. The intervention show that it has a positive effect on the student ability to understand the lesson as evident by the 7 points increase from pre to post assessment.

Summary of Results or Findings

The bargraph above shows the pretest and posttest scores of the participants. The blue line represent the The result of the pre assessment and post assessment for this research indicated that the students were really having a hard time understanding the lesson DNA structures and functions as the average scores of the student is ranging only from 8 to 11 points. After the intervention was administered during the classroom instruction, an average score of 18 points have been noticeable. The result of the post assessment shows an average score of 7 points to the participants. This result is an indicator that the students learned most after they have been exposed to manipulatives in the classroom discussion. The intervention has a positive outcome as the students begin to understand more the lesson as evident on the scores on the double bargraph above. I can say that the intervention was successful as each of the student that has participated on this research has shown confidence in identifying the structure of the DNA and it's function using the model and the scores of their post assessment increased.

Implementation

In this research, first of all I seeked the approval from the school administrators, the school principal, to do my research in the school. Students and guardians approval have been obtained as well prior to data collection for my research. The participants have been informed about the expectations and also secured a consent form from them. After all of this necessary preparations, I administered the pretest or pre assessment at the Day 1 of the research. I was able to gauge the students' knowledge on the lesson and I have used the scores to set as a baseline for the outcome of my research. The scores that I gathered served as my point of reference to see the effectiveness of the intervention.

After administering the pre test, I did the most important part which played a big role in this research, the delivery of instruction. The unit on the topic Structure of the DNA and its function was divided into four days with a maximum of one hour a day. On day 1, I set the mood of instruction by showing them a digital image of the DNA as a motivation for the lesson. The students were grouped in pairs. Each of them should have a partner that they can work with. The students showed understanding of the lesson as they became familiar with the structure of the DNA itself using the digital models. The students also exhibited understanding of the lesson by showing mastery on the definition of terms that included the function in the course of discussion on day 1. On day 2, the students were given the materials that can represent the parts of the DNA and the students started building with my step by step instruction the model of the DNA using strings and beads and plastic tubes in the classroom. The students were able to put the parts in place and were able to put them together just like how a DNA model is. On day 3, the students were able to complete the model of the DNA and labeled the parts together with their functions correctly. On day 4, the students showed mastery on the parts and were able to share the model and their style on the DNA and their function with the other group through brainstorming and sharing. After we have completed the four day instruction for the lesson, I administered the post assessment or the post test to see if the intervention that was done during the classroom instruction was effective or not. The students were given another 60 minutes to take the same assessment that was given to them during the pretest. And last step but not the least was analyzing the data that was gathered in the post test. The data analysis includes the interpretation of the learning curve after the intervention

was done. I used the baseline obtained during the pretest to compare or to check on the academic growth or learning curve of the participants.

Answer(s) to the Research Question(s)

This research have proven that yes, using manipulatives in teaching the lesson deoxyribonucleic acid or DNA structures and its function has a positive impact to the learners as evident by the average increase of 7 points to the scores of the participants.

Product

In this action research, the instructional intervention were given to the at-risk students. These students received targeted instruction to address the specific learning needs. The students were given manipulatives during the classroom instruction that they used in studying the parts of the DNA. The students have associated the models to the topic structure of DNA and its function by identifying the materials that represented its parts.

Chapter 5: Conclusions

Overview of Conclusion(s)

This research have proven that using manipulatives or object that the students can use as a representation of an idea, in teaching concepts in science like the deoxyribonucleic acid or DNA structures and its function, has a positive impact on the outcome of the students learning process. The scores, as shown on the bar graph, indicated that there was a 7 points increase on the average score of the students on thier pretest compare to their posttest. This numbers is very evident to all the 20 students pretest and posttest scores, coded A to T, who participated in completing this study. No doubt that I will be using manipulatives in the future discussion of this topic as the impact was abdolutely positive to the learners. Also, this method in teaching this topic will be recommended as well to the other teachers in my department as it has been proven effective on this particular research. This is helpful in providing support to the learners who need to study the concept in preparation for a more advance lesson in Biology.

Strengths and Weaknesses of Methodology

The methodology used in this research is quantitative. I have the same pre assessment and post assessment set of questionnaires that gave me consistent, precise and reliable data. I was able to get all the important facts from numerical data by analyzing them. Another strength using quantitative research is that data are relatively easy to analyze. The number can speak for itself if the strategy applied on the research was a success or not making it more valuable to the entirety of the study. On the other hand, using quantitative research can have weaknesses too. With this type of research method,

the outcome of your product are less detailed as it is only focus on numerical responses. Another weakness of using quantitative research methodology is that the data that you will gather maybe difficult to understand or explain complex issues as it is only focus on to what and to what extent the research could go but lacking the ability to answer the questions why or how.

Influential Factors

Some factors have definitely molded the results of this research. One factor that I consider is timing of the research implementation. It was given right at the time when there was a game. The class size of our school are comparably lower compare to a regular class size in a classroom. Some of the students are a little ditracted for sports during the implementation of this study. Another factor I consider is the student distribution in class. We have a huge number of students for both freshmen and sophomore class and as a result, the school resorted on mixing both freshmen and sophomore in Earth Science and Biology classes to make sure that classes will not be overcrowded. Some of the students who participated in this research went straight to Biology class from their their middle school science. Instead of the usual process which is to take Earth Science first before taking Biology class.

Recommendations for Further Investigation

This research was done using only quantitative data or quantitative methodology. My recommendation the next time that this research will be done is to use qualitative research or to include some qualitative aspect that would require interviewing the participants about the process of using the model and whether the students like using the model at all.

Barriers or Limitations to Drawing Conclusions

In this research, I have a small sample as not all the students are able to turn in their parental consent signed by the parents. This is one of the barriers and limitations to this research that impacted my ability to draw conclusion. Having been said that I only have 20 participants, it has limited my ability to draw conclusion and make the data generalizable because the sample size of the participant was too small. Another barrier and limitation that I think has impacted my ability to draw conclusion on this research is the number of hours I have allotted for the lesson. I can say that the hours should have been more than the 4 hours only that I have allotted on the lesson. I think additional two hours would greatly improved the scores of the students on the posttest.

Implications of Research on Educational Practice

Based on the increase of the average scores on each students that participated in this research, I can say that this is a successful study. It is a strategy that I will be using everytime that I will be teaching the lesson deoxyribonucleic acid or DNA structures and its function as the outcome has positively impacted the students acquisition of learning. I would recommend that other teachers should adopt the strategy as the students scores has greatly improved based on the outcome of the post-assessment given to the participants.

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Appendix A

In this research I have allotted 4 hours of classroom instructions. This does not include the day for the pretest and the posttest which if we will count as part of the allocated hours will be the 5th and 6th hour. On day 1 which was a full 60 minutes was given to the students to answer the questions in the pretest. This is to have a baseline for the study that I am conducting. Each participant were given the entire hour to answer each of the questions. On day 2, is when the start of the implementation of the research begins. It was a 60 minutes hour period and this was used in self exploration. I showed digital images and pictures that made the student aware of what a DNA looks like and its function. The students also brainstorm among themselves to get ideas that are interesting and share it to class. On the third day, it was a 60 minute class instruction and the students were given all the concepts and have been given all the scientific words that is related to the lesson to make them familiar with the terms that they will be taught for the unit. Also, all those vocabulary that were mentioned on day 2 were addressed. On day 4, this was another 60 minutes. The students were given the materials that they will be using to create their DNA model. The students were able to make their own model of DNA on time and managed to show it to their classmates. On day 5, the students were able to identify the structure that they created and give their functions too. This day we also used 60 minutes. Some of the students finished early and they used the remaining time to finished their work from their vocabulary work on day 2. On day 6, all students were given another 60 minutes to do the posttest.

Appendix B

Pretest in Biology

Structure of DNA and its Function

Name: _____ Period: _____ Date: _____ Score: _____

Direction– Choose the letter of the best answer. Write your answer on the space provided.

___1. What is the structure of DNA?

- a. Single helix b. double helix c. triple helix d. double dog dare

___2. What does DNA stand for?

- a. Deoxy ribonucleic acid b. delta ribonucleic c. deoxy ribose d. deoxy nucleic acid

___3. The process by which one type of bacteria is changed into another type is called

- a. Transcription b. transformation c. duplication d. replication

___4. Who discovered the DNA structure?

- a. Chargaff b. Franklin c. Watson and Crick d. Pauling

___5. Bacteriophages are

- a. A form of bacteria b. enzymes c. coils of DNA d. viruses

___6. Who behind the famous photo 51 that resulted in the discovery of the shape of DNA?

- a. Chargaff b. Franklin c. Watson and Crick d. Pauling

___7. A nucleotide does not contain

- a. 5-carbon sugar b. an amino acid c. a nitrogen base d. a phosphate group

___8. What do you call the 5-carbon sugar that can be found in the DNA?

- a. Ribose b. glucose c. lactose d. sucrose

___9. According to Chargaff, which two nitrogenous bases are equal?

- a. A and G b. G and C c. A and T d. T and C

___10. It unwinds the helix in the DNA

- a. Helicase b. DNA polymerase c. RNA Primase d. Ligase
- ___11. It is the building block of the backbone chains in the nucleic acids
- a. DNA and RNA b. Sugar c. protein d. insulin
- ___12. It is a compound consisting of a nucleoside linked to a phosphate group
- a. Nucleus b. nucleolus c. nucleotide d. nuclei
- ___13. In eukaryotes, the DNA is found in the
- a. Cytoplasm b. nucleus c. ribosome d. histones
- ___14. In prokaryotes, the DNA is found in the
- a. Cytoplasm b. nucleus c. ribosome d. histones
- ___15. Along with the sugars and bases, it makes up nucleic acids like DNA and RNA
- a. Phospholipids b. photosynthesis c. phosphate group d. photography
- ___16. What are the 4 nitrogenous bases that can be found in the DNA
- a. Adenine, Thymine/Uracil, Cytosine and Guanine
- b. Adenine, Thymine/Uracil, Cyanide and Guanine
- c. Adelaide, Thymine, Cytosine and Guanine
- d. Adenine, Thymine/Uracil, Cyanide and Guadalupe
- ___17. The main enzyme involved in linking individual nucleotides into DNA molecule is
- a. DNA protease b. Ribose c. Cytoplasm d. Histones
- ___18. Whose researcher used radioactive markers in experiments to show that DNA was the genetic materials in cell?
- a. Griffith b. Avery c. Hershey and Chase d. Watson and Crick
- ___19. How many carbons sugar are there in Ribose that makes up the DNA?
- a. 3 b. 4 c. 5 d. 6
- ___20. The order of the nitrogen bases on the DNA molecule is known as the
- a. Genetic code b. da vinci's code c. course code d. barcode
- ___21. It is made up of a long strand of DNA molecules
- a. Gene chromosomes c. allele d. adenine

- ___22. A section of DNA on a chromosome which provides proteins that determines traits
- a. Allele
 - b. gene
 - c. nitrogen base
 - d. phosphate
- ___23. Two versions of the same genes are known as
- a. Allele
 - b. chromosomes
 - c. genetic codes
 - d. barcodes
- ___24. What is the first step of replication?
- a. The DNA molecule separates
 - b. B. sugar and phosphorous bonds together
 - c. Free nitrogen bases begin to pair
 - d. Will have to to skip. There is no first step
- ___25. Adenine pairs with
- a. Thymine
 - b. cytosine
 - c. guanine
 - d. adenine
- ___26. Cytosine pairs with
- a. Thymine
 - b. cytosine
 - c. guanine
 - d. adenine
- ___27. Thymine pairs with
- a. Thymine
 - b. cytosine
 - c. guanine
 - d. adenine
- ___28. Guanine pairs with
- a. Thymine
 - b. cytosine
 - c. guanine
 - d. adenine
- ___29. What is the function of DNA primase in DNA replication
- a. Adds a short DNA primer to the template strand
 - b. Removes a short RNA primer from the template strand
 - c. Removes a short DNA primer from the template strand
 - d. Adds a short RNA primer to the template strand
- ___30. What applies to DNA base sequences?
- a. Some genes do not code for proteins
 - b. Promoters are transcribed along with the gene
 - c. Start and stop codons are not transcribed

- d. All DNA encodes for proteins

Posttest in Biology

Structure of DNA and its Function

Name: _____ Period: _____ Date: _____ Score: _____

Direction– Choose the letter of the best answer. Write your answer on the space provided.

___1. What is the structure of DNA?

- a. Single helix b. double helix c. triple helix d. double dog dare

___2. What does DNA stand for?

- a. Deoxy ribonucleic acid b. delta ribonucleic c. deoxy ribose d. deoxy nucleic acid

___3. The process by which one type of bacteria is changed into another type is called

- a. Transcription b. transformation c. duplication d. replication

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- b. Phospholipids b. photosynthesis c. phosphate group d. photography
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- h. Adenine, Thymine/Uracil, Cyanide and Guadalupe
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- b. DNA protease b. Ribose c. Cytoplasm d. Histones
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- ___22. A section of DNA on a chromosome which provides proteins that determines traits

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- g. Start and stop codons are not transcribed
- h. All DNA encodes for proteins

Appendix C

Child Assent Form

My name is Mr. Rodolfo Balagtas and the purpose of my Capstone Research Project is to determine if the instructional intervention is going to be effective in addressing the gap in the needs of the high school Biology students on understanding the topic the structures of the DNA and its function.

If you agree to join my research project, you will be asked to take a pretest and a posttest related to the topic before and after the discussion of the lesson. In this research you will be given intervention materials that would help you understand the topic well. In this research you might feel a little pressure while taking the test. As a result of participation in this research project, you do not have to answer questions that make you uncomfortable and feel free to approach me as needed.

[In this research, I will be the sole person that will have access on your score results for both assessment that you will be taking. The test results together with the test materials will be stored in my isolation room for safekeeping, away from the eyes of many.

You do not have to participate in this research project unless you choose to do so. Even if you begin the project, you may stop at any time.

You may ask questions about the project at any time, and I can answer any questions you have before you sign this form. You can send me an email at Rodolfo.balagtas@dishciibikoh.org or send me a text message or call me at my phone number +1(928) 201-5179.

_____ **YES.** I want to join this project. I understand the project will be done during normal teaching hours and classroom routines and will not disrupt my learning. I understand that even if I check "yes" now, I can change my mind later and stop participating.

Type or spell Child's
Name

[Date]

Child's Signature

[Date]

X

Signature of
Student Investigator

[Date]

X

Parent/Guardian Permission Form

I am a Student Investigator who seeks your permission for your child to participate in a Capstone Research Project entitled The Effects of Using Manipulatives in Classroom Teaching. The purpose of this Capstone Research Project is to determine if the instructional intervention is going to be effective in addressing the gap in the needs of the high school Biology students on understanding the topic the structures of the DNA and its function. The Capstone Research Project will involve approximately 10 males and 10 females' students. Your child can participate in this project if they:

- Are taking Biology subject for 10th grade in high school
- Age ranges from 14 – 16 years old

If you give permission for your child to participate in this project, your child will be asked to take a pretest and a posttest related to the topic before and after the discussion of the lesson.

Your child's participation in this project is strictly voluntary. Your decision whether or not to give permission for them to participate will not affect their current or future relations with Dishchiibikoh High School. If you initially decide to give permission to participate, you are free to withdraw permission at any time later without affecting those relationships.

There is *no more than minimal risk* associated with participating in this research project, which means participation in this project does not involve risks for your child beyond those associated with normal day-to-day living. While there is no individual benefit to your child for participation in the project, findings may provide the overall benefit of using different interventions in teaching lessons in the classroom.

In the event your child experiences stress or anxiety during their participation in the project, they may terminate participation at any time. They may also refuse to answer any questions you consider invasive or stressful. No questions aside from what is related to the topic the structure of the DNA and its function should be asked throughout the execution of this research.

Your child's participation involves collection of the test results from both assessments that they will be taking prior and after the discussion of the lesson. If you decline for your child to be recorded, they will/will not be permitted to participate in the project.

Any data or records gathered from your child's participation will be kept private and confidential. Any identifiable data gathered will be coded to protect your child's identity. Each subject that may lead to identify the students who participated in this program will be recoded to a generic one. Research records will be securely stored and only accessible to the researcher.

Please ask any questions related to this permission for your child's participation. If you or your child have questions later, you may contact me via email at Rodolfo.balagtas@dishciibikoh.org or send me a text message or call me at my phone number +1(928) 201-5179 or the WGU IRB at IRB@WGU.EDU.

Parent/Guardian Permission

I, _____, a parent/guardian of _____, a minor-aged child, have read the above information, have been given adequate time to consider the information, and understand my child may stop participation at any point. I have asked questions and received answers. I give permission for my child to participate in this research project. I understand I will be offered a copy of this signed form.

Typed Name of
Parent/Guardian

[Date]

Parent/Guardian
Signature

[Date]

X

Signature of
Student Investigator

[Date]

X

Parent/Guardian Permission

I have read the above information, been given adequate time to consider the information, and understand my child's participation is voluntary so they may stop participation at any point. I have asked questions and received answers. I give permission for my child to take part in this project and understand I will be offered a copy of the completed form.

Yes

No

Dishchiibikoh Community School

211 s. Elm Circle-P.O. Box 80068

Cibecue, AZ 85911

Phone: 928-332-2444

Fax: 928-332-2341

September 21, 2022

Dear Rodolfo Balagtas II:

We have reviewed your request regarding your study and am pleased to support your Capstone Research Project entitled "The Effects of Using Manipulatives in Classroom Instruction." Dishchiibikoh Community School agrees to collaborate with you for data collection. The study involves collecting data results from pretest and posttest after the intervention has been administered to the 10th grade students in high school taking Biology class for the topic structures of the DNA and its function.

This permission covers the time period of October 17 to October 21, 2022. We look forward to supporting your capstone research. We understand your study requires the determination of the Western Governors Institutional Review Board as exempt research and data collection will not begin until this determination is received.

Sincerely,

Mr. Phil Endfield

Dishchiibikoh MS/HS Principal

Dischiibikoh High School

928-332-2444 ext. 1413